

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENDOPHYTIC BACTERIA IN THE CONTROL OF FUSARIUM DISEASE IN WHEAT

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ABSTRACT

This text analyzes the ecological diversity of endophytic microorganisms living within internal plant tissues and their role in the biological protection of wheat crops against pathogenic fungi belonging to the genus Fusarium. The study substantiates the high efficiency of antagonist microorganisms such as Bacillus subtilis, Pseudomonas fluorescens, and Streptomyces in controlling fusarium disease. Biologically active lipopeptides, including surfactin, fengycin, and mycosubtilin synthesized by Bacillus strains, have been shown to disrupt the cell membrane of pathogens and promote plant growth. Furthermore, the importance of the temperature factor in optimizing biopreparations and the prospects of artificial intelligence technologies for early disease detection are discussed.

Endophytic microorganisms include a diverse group of bacteria and fungi that live in the internal tissues of plants, coexisting without causing significant harm to the host. These bacteria form complex and often symbiotic relationships with plants, which significantly improve the physiology, adaptability and survival of plants in many environmental situations. In contrast to epiphytic microorganisms that live on plant surfaces, endophytes penetrate internal tissues, including roots, stems, leaves and reproductive organs, creating complex ecological networks in plant systems [1].

Plant tissue colonization by endophytes is often a tightly controlled process. Microorganisms enter the plant through natural openings such as stomata and lenticels, or through the root zone, especially where lateral roots develop. In some cases, entry can occur through wounds or mechanical damage. Effective colonization during invasion depends on the ability of the microorganism to evade or regulate plant immune responses. This is often accomplished by the release of signaling molecules and enzymes that mediate host-bacterial compatibility [2].

Endophytic microorganisms, including many bacterial genera such as Bacillus, Pseudomonas, Enterobacter, Azospirillum, and Burkholderia, exhibit considerable taxonomic diversity. Fungal endophytes play an important role in this category, including species such as Fusarium, Penicillium, and Aspergillus. The diversity of endophytes depends on the plant species, environmental conditions, geographic location, and developmental stage of the host plant. This diversity is a key feature of their functional adaptability [3].

Wheat is one of the agricultural crops that is of great importance in ensuring the food security of the world's population. However, phytopathogenic fungi of the *Fusarium* genus reduce wheat yield and cause the accumulation of mycotoxins in the grain [4]. *Fusarium* wilt affects the ear, root and stem parts of wheat. As a result, plant growth slows down, yields decrease, and economic losses occur. Therefore, it is important to develop effective protective measures against the disease. Currently, one of the environmentally friendly methods is biological control. Antagonist microorganisms inhibit the development of pathogenic fungi and activate the natural defense system of the plant [5].

Field experiments conducted by Palazzini et al. showed that beneficial bacteria significantly reduced the development of *Fusarium graminearum* [4]. The results of the study showed the practical value of biological preparations. According to the studies of Lu Z. et al., *Bacillus subtilis* BS45 strain suppresses the growth of fungal mycelium and reduces the formation of spores. Biologically active metabolites produced by *Bacillus subtilis* affect the cell membrane of pathogens and disrupt their vital activity [6].

Wang et al. found that the SG6 strain has high antagonistic activity and produces substances such as surfactin and fengycin [7]. Nourozian et al. studied the effectiveness of *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, and *Streptomyces* species against the causative agent of fusarium wilt and noted that these microorganisms significantly reduce the development of the disease [8].

Endophytic bacteria also play an important role in plant protection. It was found that the *Bacillus* CB2 strain stimulates the growth of wheat and increases its resistance to diseases. Leclère et al. found that the mycosubtilin-producing *Bacillus subtilis* strains have high antifungal properties. These substances will serve as an important source for the creation of new biopreparations in the future. The temperature factor affects the production of biologically active substances by bacteria. Therefore, it is important to optimize the technology of biopreparation production [9].

Modern technologies are expanding the possibilities of early detection of fusariosis in wheat. Methods based on artificial intelligence are important in assessing the effectiveness of biological preparations. Thus, biopreparations based on *Bacillus subtilis* and other beneficial microorganisms are considered environmentally safe and promising means of protection against wheat fusariosis [10].

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